

3.4 Sedimentary facies analysis of fine-grained sediments

Sedimentary facies have been grouped into four facies associations i) lacustrine, ii) delta front, iii) meandering alluvial/delta plain, and iv) mire (Table 3.1) with the fifth conglomeratic alluvial fan-fan delta facies association already covered in Chapter 2. There were two purposes for conducting a detailed analysis of sedimentary facies. One was to develop better palaeogeographic reconstructions, with an emphasis on carbonaceous lacustrine facies, and how those changed through time. A secondary purpose was to adequately assign ‘transitional lithosomes’ to lacustrine or meandering alluvial environments in order to better understand the distribution of possible lacustrine source rocks in the Greymouth Basin.

3.4.1 Lacustrine facies association

The lacustrine facies association is made up of all subaqueous facies. Three subaqueous facies are identified: the lacustrine massive mudstone facies, the lacustrine mudstones with minor sandstone facies, and the sandy turbidites facies.

3.4.1.1 Massive mudstone facies

Description: The massive mudstone facies is generally massive and structureless (Figure 3.5 A). It consists primarily of highly carbonaceous, grey to black mudstone/silty mudstone with occasional purple or brown colouring. Pyrites and tuff bands are rarely present in this facies. Small leaves and freshwater fossils may be locally abundant (Figure 3.5 B and 3.5 C) but no roots are found. Freshwater molluscs from *Hyridella* species and pollen from *Nothofagus* (southern beech) species were identified by Gage (1952) and Ward (1997). This facies shows uniform high gamma-ray response. It is widely distributed throughout the Greymouth Basin and is easily identified both in outcrop and drill core (Figure 3.6). The facies is commonly associated with the mudstone with minor thin sandstones facies and sandy turbidites facies.

Interpretations: The massive mudstone facies is interpreted to have been deposited in the deep water of a freshwater lake characterized by fine-grained, relatively slow sedimentation from suspension beyond the direct influence of shoreline or deltaic processes (e.g. Anadon et al. 1991; Renaut and Gierlowski-Kordesch 2010). More recent research indicates that thick mudstones may form from muddy hyperpycnal flows loaded by turbulent suspension of silt and clay resulting in with erosional bases (Plint 2014, Zavala 2018), suggesting that the lake shore may have been closer than originally interpreted. The tuff bands found in this facies most likely fell directly on the water surface and settled to the bottom. The presence of pyrite indicates an anoxic environment and may have been formed by early diagenetic alteration within pore fluids at a shallow burial depth (Wells 1995). The *Hyridella* species molluscan fossils found in this facies indicate deposition occurred in a freshwater setting (Marshall et al. 2014). The presence of leaf fossils of genus *Banksiaeformis* and pollen such as *Nothofagus* suggests that the Late Cretaceous had an environment quite similar to that of New Zealand today (Hill and Christophel 1988; Ward 1997; Kennedy 2003; Raine et.al. 2017). The absence of roots indicates that deposition took place in deep water.

Table 3. 1: List of different facies association and their associated lithofacies of the Paparoa Formation

Facies association	Lithofacies
Lacustrine	Massive mudstone facies
	Mudstone with minor sandstone facies
	Sandy turbidite facies
Delta front	Sandy mouthbar facies
	Interdistributary bay facies
Meandering alluvial/delta plain	Meandering channel facies
	Abandoned channel facies
	Crevasse splay facies
Mires	Mire coal facies
	Low lying marshy swamp facies

Figure 3. 1: A) Massive mudstone facies of the Goldlight Member at Spring Creek Mine (Seven Mile Stream), and B) leaf fossils at 289.65m and C) fresh water molluscs fossils at 293.98m in DH-624.

Figure 3. 2: DH-649 showing lacustrine facies association with massive mudstone facies, mudstone with minor thin sandstone facies and sandy turbidites facies.

3.4.1.2 Mudstones with minor thin sandstone facies

Description: The mudstone with minor thin sandstone facies is characterized by carbonaceous mudstones interbedded with thin, brownish grey, fine sandstone and siltstone beds (10% sandstone/siltstone, 90% mudstone) (Figure 3.6 and Figure 3.7). Mudstones are light grey, purple or brown in colour and mostly 6-8 m thick. Interbedded siltstone beds are grey to dark grey and are less than 1 cm thick. Interbedded fine sandstone beds are normally graded with hints of ripple cross-laminations and are less than 3 cm thick. Coarse sandstones are occasionally found. Basal contacts of the thin sandstone or siltstone beds are commonly erosional or sometimes wavy and sharp. The upper contacts are slightly gradational with overlying mudstones. Conspicuous plant debris (~10%) is common in fine-grained sandstone beds. Freshwater molluscs from *Hyridella* species (Gage 1952) and leaves of genus *Banksiaeformis* (Hill and Christophel 1988) are occasionally present. The facies exhibits sudden low gamma-ray spikes in the overall high gamma-ray response recording the presence of the sandstone beds in the mudstones. This facies varies in thickness and can be found in both outcrops and drill cores. This facies is found in the centre of the basin and commonly associated with lacustrine massive mudstone facies.

Interpretations: The mudstone with minor thin sandstone facies is interpreted to have been deposited in a lake within the influence of irregular and rare turbidity currents. The fresh water fossils indicate a lacustrine rather than marine setting. The presence of normally graded beds with erosive or sharp bases, conspicuous plant debris, and faint ripples indicates deposition by turbidity currents (e.g. Basilici 1997; Boggs 2006; Sturm and Matter 2009). The turbidite beds likely resulted from exceptional river discharges which could deliver coarser sediments and reworked plant debris and displaced snails and other micro-fossils into deeper water where the resultant deposits became intercalated with the predominant lacustrine muds from suspension settling and/or hyperpycnal underflows (e.g. Span et.al. 1992; Basilici 1997; Renaut and Gierlowski-Kordesch 2010, Plint 2014 and Zavala 2018).

3.4.1.3 Sandy turbidites facies

Description: The sandy turbidites facies comprises mudstones (60%) regularly interbedded with sandstones (30%) and siltstones (10%) (Figure 3.7 and Figure 3.8 A). Mudstones are dark grey to brown, sandy to silty with occasional leaf fossils and minor bioturbation. Mudstone beds range in thickness between 60 cm and 8 m. Mudstones look similar to those of the lacustrine massive mudstone facies and lacustrine mudstone with minor thin sandstone facies except the presence of bioturbation and sandy to silty nature distinguish it from other lacustrine mudstones. Sandstone beds are grey, fine to medium grained, normally graded, and range in thickness from thick (~20 cm - 2 m) to thin (5 – 10 cm). Conspicuous fine plant debris (~10%) is common in fine-grained sandstone beds although coarse plant fragments are rare and roots are absent. Siltstone beds are grey to dark grey and range in thickness between 20 cm and 50 cm. Soft sediment deformation structures such as load casts are common in the siltstone and sandstone beds (Figure 3.8 B and 3.8 C). The presence of soft sediment deformation structures and relatively thicker sandstone beds distinguishes this facies from the lacustrine mudstones with minor thin sandstones facies. This facies shows a serrated pattern in the gamma-ray log. It is only found in drill cores and is primarily located in the eastern and northwestern parts of the basin. This facies is commonly associated with lacustrine massive mudstone facies.

Interpretations: The facies is interpreted to have been deposited in a lacustrine environment that was more proximal to the shoreline, probably in the prodelta region, where sedimentation rate was high and turbidity currents were common. These turbidite beds mostly belong to divisions C and D of the Bouma sequence

model. Mudstones and siltstones indicate sedimentation mainly from suspension and/or hyperpycnal underflows between turbidity current events (e.g. Renaut and Gierlowski-Kordesch 2010, Plint 2014 and Zavala 2018). Conspicuous plant debris was transported by the turbidity currents (e.g. Kelts 1988). The soft sediment deformation structures were likely caused by density differences or fluid escape in water-saturated unconsolidated sediments at the top of a slope such as in the prodelta environment (Bhattacharya 2010; Topal and Ozkul 2014).

Figure 3. 3: Mudstone with minor thin sandstone facies of the Waiomo Member at Twelve Mile Beach.

3.4.2 Delta front facies association

Two facies are identified in the delta front facies association, the sandy mouthbar facies and the interdistributary bay facies.

3.4.2.1 Sandy mouthbar facies

Description: The sandy mouthbar facies is characterized by thick, grey, coarsening and thickening upwards, fine to medium grained, sandstone beds (Figure 3.9A and Figure 3.9B). The sandstone beds are reversely graded with cross-laminations preserved in some locations. Coarse woody material (~10%) can be found in some places which has been altered to coaly fragments. There is no bioturbation and no roots present. Beds range from 30 cm to 10 m thick and show distinct channel shapes. The coarsening upward sequences are easily identifiable in gamma ray logs. The facies is mostly distributed in the eastern, central and some places of the northwestern parts of the basin. It is commonly overlain by meandering alluvial facies

association on delta plain environments and commonly underlain by sandy turbidites facies and rarely by the lacustrine massive mudstone facies. This facies can be identified in both outcrops and drill core.

Interpretations: This facies is interpreted to have been deposited in a delta front at the mouth of a river channel where it enters the low energy lake. Sandy mouthbar facies predominantly reflect deposition from rapidly decelerating unidirectional flows in distributary mouthbar environments (e.g. Reading 2009; Collinson and Lewin 2009). Reverse grading within sandstone beds combined with thickening of these beds up sequence is indicative of a prograding mouth bar environment in an alluvially dominated delta where channel enters a lake and dumps the bed load at the mouth of the channel (e.g. Makaske et al. 2002; Jones and Hajek 2007; Bhattacharya 2010).

Figure 3. 4: A) Sandy turbidites facies from 275m to 278m in DH-624; Soft sediment structures found in DH-624, B) ripple marks and load casts at 261.80m; C) load casts at 261.98m.

3.4.2.2 Interdistributary bay facies

Description: The interdistributary bay facies is characterized by mudstones and siltstones (80%) with occasional beds of sandstones (20%) (Figure 3.10). Mudstones and siltstones are moderately to weakly carbonaceous, lack leaf fossils, and are moderately to highly bioturbated. Sandstones are grey, very fine to fine grained, and carbonaceous in some places. Sandstone beds lack erosional bases, lack normal grading, and occasionally contain faint current ripple cross-lamination. Carbonaceous sandstones are found in some places. Rootlets are absent but coaly stringers are present (Figure 3.10). Isolated granule and pebble clasts are found in some places. The thickness of this facies ranges from ~70 cm to 4.5 m. In the vertical succession, the facies is commonly associated with the sandy mouthbar facies in the east and the southeast or with the gravelly mouthbar facies in the northwest (Chapter 2). An overall decrease upward in several gamma ray logs is interpreted as coarsening upward cycles, consistent with an association with mouthbar facies.

Interpretations: This facies is interpreted to have been deposited in interdistributary bays between channels in the delta front region of sandy/muddy low gradient deltas. Sedimentation occurred from settling of suspended fine-grained sediments and organic matter as indicated by the well laminated carbonaceous mudstones and siltstones (e.g. Tye and Kisters 1986). The lack of normal grading in the sandstone beds indicates that sedimentation either didn't take place from turbidity currents or the grain sizes were thoroughly mixed by the more pervasive bioturbation. The association with mouthbar facies indicates close proximity to an active river mouth where channel avulsion was common in a deltaic environment, low-gradient to the southeast and high gradient to the northwest (e.g. Makaske et al. 2002). The overall coarsening upward sequence indicates that deposition took place in the delta front region.

3.4.3 Meandering alluvial/delta plain facies association

The meandering alluvial/delta plain facies association includes meandering channel facies, abandoned channel facies and crevasse splay facies.

3.4.3.1 Meandering channel facies

Description: The meandering channel facies is composed of grey to light grey, moderately to well sorted, fine to medium grained sandstones. Occasional granule to pebble conglomerates and coarse to very coarse sandstones are present in some places. The sandstone units range from thick (~1-7.5 m) to thin (~10 cm -1 m) and show distinct channel shapes. Basal scours are found in most of the channels. Coarse coaly fragments and other plant material (~5-10%) are also present. Crossbedding structures are very common in this facies and are well preserved in outcrops and drill cores (Figure 3.11A, 3.11B and 3.11C). In some places, lateral accretion structures can be seen. In gamma ray log, this facies shows multiple fining upward trends as this facies is commonly associated with overlying abandoned channel facies and crevasse splay facies (Figure 3.12 and Figure 3.13). The meandering channel facies is mainly found in the central, eastern and southwestern parts of the Greymouth Basin.

Interpretations: This facies is interpreted to have been deposited in channels in an alluvial environment where unidirectional current flow was the dominant depositional process as indicated by cross-bedding. The thick sandstone units are interpreted to have been deposited from continuous but variable flow in a river channel. The distinct channel shapes with basal scours and lag deposits, the presence of crossbeds and lateral accretion beds, and overall fining upward sequences indicate meandering channel deposits (Reading 2009; Miall 2010). The meandering channel facies was deposited in both delta plain settings

when lakes were present in the basin and on alluvial plains when there were no lakes or the lakeshore was more distal.

Figure 3. 5: Sandy mouthbar facies A) reverse graded sandstone beds within the Goldlight Member at Ten Mile Creek; B) coarsening upwards sandstone beds in DH-656.

Figure 3. 6: Interdistributary bay facies at Twelve Mile Beach showing bioturbation from burrows in sandstone and siltstones.

Figure 3. 7: A) alternating meandering channel with hints of cross-beds and abandoned channel facies of the Rewanui Member are found inside the tunnel section at Seven Mile Creek Road (modified from Davies 2019), B) cross bedding structure in meandering channel from the lower part of the tunnel section at Seven Mile Creek Road, C) core from DH-637 showing cross lamination in a meandering channel fill are found at 271.3 m in DH-637.

3.4.3.2 Abandoned channel facies

Description: The abandoned channel facies consists of muddy sandstones (20%) with silty carbonaceous mudstone to highly carbonaceous mudstone (50%) fining up to muddy coals at the top (30%) (Figure 3.12 and Figure 3.13). This facies occurs in channel shape lenses. Sandstones are very fine grained and the bed thickness ranges between 20 cm and 3 m. The carbonaceous mudstone beds range from a minimum 20 cm to maximum 2 m. Coals are high in ash content and coal beds range from minimum 40 cm to maximum 1 m. Occasional thin beds of fine sandstones may be present in the mudstones. Rootlets are common in this facies. This facies shows a fining upward nature in the gamma ray log. The coal beds show a positive spike in the density log. The facies commonly overlies the sandy meandering channel facies. The abandoned channel facies is mainly found in the central, eastern and southwestern parts of the Greymouth Basin.

Interpretations: This facies is interpreted to have been deposited in abandoned channels which were once the main channel in a meandering river. After abandonment the channel remained as an oxbow lake or a wetland for a substantial length of time as indicated by the presence of muddy sandstones at the bottom and carbonaceous mudstones or muddy coals at the top. Channel abandonment is a common process in meandering alluvial systems and results from channel shifting processes such as meander cut-off and channel-belt avulsion (Slingerland and Smith 2003; Miall 2010; Toonen et. al., 2012). The presence of laminated carbonaceous mudstone suggests slow sedimentation where the organic material is mixed with mud and deposited. Occasional thin beds of sandstone indicate periodic flood events (Bridge 1984; O'Brien and Wells 1986). High ash content indicates episodic input of clastic sediments into the swamps or oxbow lakes from river flooding. The presence of coals indicates the balance among sediment supply, basin subsidence rate and rate of decomposition of the organic matter. Slow decomposition rate of the organic matter retains most of its carbon, suggesting its potentiality as petroleum source rocks. This facies is common in the interpreted delta plain when lakes were present in the basin as well as in non-deltaic alluvial environments when there were no lakes in the basin.

3.4.3.3 Crevasse splay facies

Description: The crevasse splay facies comprises inversely to normally graded, medium to fine sandstone beds (~40-50%) interbedded with laminated silty mudstone to carbonaceous mudstones (~30-40%) with abundant plant material and rootlets (~10-20%) (Figure 3.14A). Sandstones are grey to light grey in colour and contain occasional small cross-beds and ripple marks. Basal scours with underlying beds are not very common but are found in some localities. The individual beds range in thickness from 1 cm to 10 cm thick. However, gross thicknesses of crevasse splay facies ranges from minimum 10 m to maximum 35 m when associated with other floodplain facies. The facies shows coarsening to fining upwards trends in gamma ray logs (Figure 3.12, Figure 3.13 and Figure 3.14B). The facies is commonly overlain and underlain by meandering channel facies and abandoned channel facies, and is mostly found in the central and the eastern sides of the basin.

Interpretations: The facies is interpreted to have been deposited on a floodplain in close proximity to an active channel where excess discharge during flooding incises the adjacent levee and deposits as a splay (e.g. Allen 1965; Elliott 1974; Guion 1985). The sandstone beds are interpreted as channelized crevasse splays whereas laminated mudstone and siltstones are interpreted as flood plain deposits (e.g. Bridge 1984). Basal scours indicate the sandstones were deposited from flood events (e.g. O'Brien and Wells 1986). Mudstones and siltstones were deposited from sediment settling when the flooding ceased and water remained stagnant in small depressions for a long time. Coarsening upwards sequences are the product of

levee or splay prograding into the flood basin areas whereas fining upward sequences are produced by abandonment of individual crevasse channel (e.g. Bridge 1984). The association of sandy meandering channel facies over- and under-lying this facies may indicate that the avulsion of a meandering channel was a common process in the Greymouth Basin (e.g. Slingerland and Smith 2003). This facies was deposited in both deltaic and non-deltaic settings when there were lakes in the basin and there were no lakes in the basin, respectively.

Figure 3. 8: Thick deposits of alternating meandering channel, abandoned channel and crevasse splay facies of meandering alluvial/delta plain facies association of the Rewanui Member are found in DH-658. Meandering channel and abandoned channel facies are showing fining upward trends in gamma ray log whereas coarsening to fining upwards trends are representing crevasse splay facies.

Figure 3. 9: An axial meandering and floodplain system of the Rewanui Member shows alternating meandering channel, abandoned channel and crevasse splay facies of meandering alluvial/delta plain facies association at the Seven Mile Creek road cut section (modified from Davies 2019). Channel sandstones exhibit hints of cross-beds with mostly southerly palaeoflow directions.

Figure 3. 10: A) Crevasse splay facies at Spring Creek Haul Road, and B) Gamma log showing crevasse splay facies with coarsening and finning upward sequences in DH-656.

3.4.4 Mire facies association

The mire facies association includes the mire coal facies and the low-lying marshy swamp facies. In the basin axis, this facies association is found in the upper part of each alluvial member (Jay, Morgan, Rewanui and Dunollie).

3.4.4.1 Mire coal facies

Description: The mire coal facies comprises two subfacies; the first is characterized by black, hard, thick, and clean coals (Figure 3.15A) whereas the second is characterised by alternating bands of clean coals and muddy/dirty coals. The thick clean coals are low in ash and sulphur content. The thick coal seams are typically up to 11 m thick (range 3m-11m) and are lenticular in shape, most having a maximum lateral extent of about 1.5 km (Edbrooke 2000). The clean coal exhibits a uniform nature both in gamma and bulk density logs (Figure 3.15B). The alternating bands of clean and muddy coals show high ash content and low to moderate sulphur values. Pebble layers and isolated pebbles are common. The thicknesses of the alternating clean/muddy coals range from a minimum of 20 cm to a maximum of 3 m. They exhibit a discrete nature in the gamma ray log and a positive spike in the density log (Figure 3.15B). Both subfacies are commonly associated with low lying marshy swamp facies and meandering floodplain facies. The facies is mostly distributed in the basin centre.

Interpretations: The facies is interpreted to have been deposited in mire environments where the drainage systems are poorly developed, inhibited by vegetation, and so the clastic input is very low (e.g. Diessel

1992). The very low sediment supply and low bacterial decomposition helps to preserve the organic material in the mire which, upon burial, becomes thick clean coals. The low ash and low sulphur contents of the thick coals indicate they were probably deposited in raised mire conditions where rainfall exceeded evaporation and organic growth was rapid (McCabe 1984; Moore 1987). In addition, rain water is poor in sulphate, is naturally oxygenated, and has low pH (< 7) which reduces sulphate bacteria and thus inhibits bacterial activity resulting in the low sulphur content of this facies (e.g. Casagrande 1987; Gruber and Sachsenhofer 2001). The lack of a detrital influx during flood events, as indicated by the low ash content, probably requires a mire to be raised topographically above the floodplain (e.g. Gruber and Sachsenhofer 2001). The abundance of high ash in the alternating clean and muddy coals indicates that deposition took place in a topographically lower floodplain environment, probably in a low-lying mire setting where minor, low energy, distributary channels brought in sediment during flood events. The presence of pebble layers and isolated pebbles are an indication of larger flood events. The low to moderate sulphur content in the alternating clean/muddy coals suggests a fresh water environment (e.g. Sachsenhofer and Gruber 2001). The raised mire coal facies commonly grades laterally as well as vertically into low lying mire coal facies (McCabe 1984; Moore 1987; Diessel 1992).

3.4.4.2 Low-lying marshy swamp facies

Description: The low-lying marshy swamp facies usually comprises low to high carbonaceous mudstones (~40%), interlaminated with variably carbonaceous siltstones and mudstones (~40%) with abundant roots, twigs and other plant remains (~20%) (Figure 3.13B, Figure 3.16A and Figure 3.16B). Thin beds of carbonaceous, muddy, very fine-grained sandstone are occasionally present. Bioturbation from burrows is common. Laminations are distorted mostly by plant roots and bioturbation (Figure 3.16B). The thickness of this facies ranges from a minimum of 5m to a maximum of 30 m. In general, it shows relatively higher values in the gamma ray log than clean coals because of the presence of fine-grained mudstones and siltstones. This facies also shows serrated nature in gamma ray log because of its association with alternating bands of thin coal beds. In most drill holes, this facies is interbedded with the mire coal facies and may be underlain by the mire coal facies and overlain by the lacustrine massive mudstone facies. The facies is distributed in the centre and the northeastern side of the basin but is more common in the basin centre.

Interpretations: This facies is interpreted to have been deposited in wet and low energy areas, probably in a low-lying mire setting in a lower delta plain or along a lake shore. This facies also deposited in low lying areas in a non-deltaic setting. Water depth in these low-lying areas was extremely shallow and marshy (e.g. Coleman et al. 1964). The laminations of carbonaceous mudstones and siltstones indicate a low energy environment where deposition mainly occurred from the settlement of suspended fine-grained clastic material and plant remains. The extremely shallow, marshy environment was favourable for growing vegetation as indicated by the presence of abundant roots. The presence of bioturbation suggests that oxygen levels were high enough to favour the development of burrows (e.g. Bann et al. 2008). The rarity of sandy clastic sediments indicates that the facies was deposited away from an active river system.

3.5 Distribution of sedimentary facies

The fence diagram (Figure 3.17) illustrates the distribution of sedimentary facies across the Greymouth Basin. In the basin's centre, sedimentary facies alternate between lacustrine / shoreline facies associations, corresponding to the lacustrine members (Ford, Waiomo, and Goldlight), and meandering alluvial / mire facies associations, corresponding to the coal-bearing members (Jay, Morgan, Rewanui, and Dunollie). The

margins of the basin contain only meandering alluvial and fan delta/alluvial fan facies associations (Chapter 2) of the coal-bearing members (Jay, Morgan, Rewanui, and Dunollie).

During deposition of the lacustrine members, thick deposits of the lacustrine facies association were formed in the centre of the basin comprising the lacustrine massive mudstone facies and the lacustrine mudstones with minor thin sandstones facies grading laterally to the shallower water sandy turbidites facies. Shorelines are indicated by the presence of deltaic sandy mouthbar facies and interdistributary bay facies as well as low lying marshy swamp facies. The northwestern side of the basin was dominated by fan delta facies (Chapter 2) whereas the southern and eastern sides of the basin were dominated by meandering alluvial delta plain facies association comprising meandering channel, abandoned channel, and crevasse splay facies.

Figure 3. 11: A) Mire coal facies in the Rewanui Member at Roa Mine, B) mire coal facies and associated low lying marshy swamp facies in DH-624.

Figure 3. 12: A) Presence of roots and bioturbation in fine grained muddy sandstone in low lying marshy swamp facies at Spring Creek Haul Road, B) Presence of rootlets in laminated carbonaceous mudstone and siltstone in low lying marshy swamp facies at 54.16 m in DH-624.

During deposition of the coal-bearing alluvial members, the centre and southern side of the basin were dominated by the meandering alluvial facies association comprising meandering channel facies, abandoned channel facies and crevasse splay facies (Figure 3.12 and Figure 3.13). Palaeocurrent measurements on cross-beds from the meandering channel facies show palaeoflow was to the south-southwest (Figure 3.13; Davies 2019). The eastern side of the basin was also dominated by the meandering alluvial facies association. The northwestern side of the basin was dominated by the alluvial fan facies association indicating steep topography from the uplifted fault scarp (Chapter 2).

During the transitions from lacustrine to alluvial members, mire coal facies and low-lying marshy swamp facies commonly replaced the lacustrine massive mudstone facies in the centre of the basin. In most places, low-lying marshy swamp facies overlies thick lacustrine facies association. The opposite happened during transitions from alluvial to lacustrine members; the mire facies association is overlain by the lacustrine massive mudstone facies in the centre of the basin.

3.6 Interpretation of palaeogeography

The deposition of the thickest alluvial fan and fan delta conglomerate facies on the northwest side of the basin indicates a steep topography in the northwest, most likely fault-controlled (Chapter 2). The lacustrine massive mudstone facies in the basin centre indicates the presence of lakes. The meandering alluvial/delta plain facies association dominates the southeastern margin of the basin indicating a landscape of sandy to muddy meandering river deltas formed on a low gradient topographic slope. Meandering alluvial deltas also would have entered the lakes from the southwest and northeast delineating the overall size of the lakes. The lacustrine mudstones were thickest in the basin centre and onlap fan delta conglomerates and

meandering alluvial delta sandstones as lakes gradually expanded during maximum flooding during deposition of the lacustrine members.

The meandering alluvial facies association periodically replaced the lacustrine facies association in the basin's centre with palaeo-flow parallel to the fault controlled steep topography indicating an axial meandering river and floodplain. Meandering alluvial facies association dominates the southeastern margin of the basin suggesting meandering river tributary systems that flowed from the southeast into an axial meandering river. Alluvial fan facies association dominates the northwestern margin of the basin indicating steep topography existed in that area. The presence of the mire facies association in the basin centre over- and under lying lacustrine mudstone facies association indicates the transition into or out of alluvial phases in the basin.

Figure 3. 13: Fence diagram illustrates the distribution of different sedimentary facies of three lacustrine mudstone and four coal-bearing members of the Papanoa Formation of the Greymouth Basin.

The sedimentary facies analysis indicates that shoreline and shallow water facies are more difficult to identify and categorize compared to the deep lacustrine organic facies as they show lateral complexities when associated with other similar-looking subaerial facies. One of the important tasks in this chapter was to re-examine the “transitional lithosomes” defined by Ward (1997) in order to recognize and differentiate

shoreline and subaqueous lacustrine facies. The transitional lithosomes were defined as “interbedded mudstones, siltstones and coarsening upward, fine to medium sandstones with soft sediment deformation structures, fresh water bivalve impressions, leaf fossils, fine detritus and rare thin carbonaceous mudstone beds” and interpreted as subaqueous lacustrine delta by Ward (1997). Detailed sedimentary facies analysis indicates that the “transitional lithosomes” as defined by Simon Ward (1997) are mostly of the sandy turbidites facies, sandy mouthbar facies, and interdistributary bay facies deposited in low gradient meandering river deltas, and low-lying marshy swamp facies deposited away from the deltas. The inclusion of the sandy turbidites facies as lacustrine facies will enlarge the volume of lacustrine facies association in the Greymouth Basin.

The palaeogeography of the Greymouth Basin can be compared with the landscape proposed in half-graben basin models (Model A and Model B) by Leeder and Gawthorpe (1987) (Figure 3.18). Model A represents a continental rift basin with fan deltas on the steep, fault-controlled side, lake in the basin axis, and low gradient, sandy, deltas fed by meandering rivers on the hinge side of the basin. When compared to the Greymouth Basin, the three lacustrine members (Ford, Waiomo, and Goldlight) were most likely deposited in this setting where the lacustrine facies association can be found in the basin axis indicating an asymmetric depo-centre, the correlative alluvial fan/fan-delta facies association during lacustrine deposition can be found to the northwest indicating the presence of steeper, fault-controlled topography, and the correlative sandy/muddy meandering alluvial/delta plain facies association at the time of lacustrine deposition can be found on the southeastern side of the basin indicating the location of the half-graben hinge. Model B illustrates a continental basin with axial meandering river and floodplain during the time when no lake was present in the basin. When applied to the Greymouth Basin, the four alluvial members (Jay, Morgan, Rewanui, and Dunollie) were likely deposited in a half-graben setting similar to Model B. The alluvial fan facies association was deposited along the steeper, fault-controlled northwestern margin whereas axial meandering rivers with mire coals and low-lying marshy swamp facies gradually replacing the lacustrine facies association in the basin centre. Sandy meandering rivers and floodplains continued to occupy the southeastern margin of the basin.

The alternating meandering alluvial and lacustrine facies in the centre of the Greymouth Basin are likely to have been the product of changes in subsidence rate (Figure 3.18). The presence or absence of a lake in the centre of the basin records variation in accommodation conditions (A) in the basin and the balance between sediment supply (S) and subsidence through time (Leeder and Gawthorpe 1987; Plint 2001; Martins-Neto and Catuneanu 2010; Holz et. al. 2015, 2017). The creation of a lake in the basin centre records conditions when the sedimentation rate was too low to fill the accommodation space ($A > S$) created from periods of more rapid subsidence. This interpretation assumes the sediment supply was relatively constant through time as indicated by the lack of climate change during deposition in the Greymouth Basin (Hill and Christophel 1988; Ward 1997; Kennedy 2003; Raine et.al. 2017). These periods of rapid subsidence were followed by periods of slow subsidence when sediment supply was greater than the creation of accommodation space ($A < S$) and the palaeolakes gradually filled with sediments. The resulting landscape was dominated by an axial meandering river and floodplain system with alluvial fan and meandering rivers entering from the sides of the basin. The back and forth of the variable subsidence rates of the basin give rise the alternating deposition of alluvial and lacustrine sediments through time with the economically productive mires deposited during the transitions.

Figure 3. 14: Palaeogeography of the Greymouth Basin, Model A represents the landscape when there was a lake in the basin centre whereas Model B illustrates the landscape when axial meandering river and floodplain systems dominated the basin centre.

